

Project Planning Practices and Business Success in Community-Based Initiatives

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Abstract:- The study was carried out to analyze Project planning practices and business success in community-based initiatives. Primary data for the study was collected from Abahizi Community Benefit Project (CBP) located in Marembo Village, Nyamyumba cell, Masoro Sector, Rulindo District in the Northern Province of Rwanda and secondary data are obtained from books and journals. The general objective for this research was to analyze the impact of effective project management practices on overall business success while the specific objectives of this study are to investigate the impact of project planning on business success. A null hypotheses was formulated and letter was rejected. To understand various concepts the study presents a Theoretical review, an Empirical review and Conceptual Framework. In addition, a study universe of 199 people was chosen from which 199 respondents who were purposively chosen to provide answers through a questionnaire. Data collected was obtained from 177 respondents. For data analysis, the study employed the regression model to study the various construct project management. The study revealed that performing project planning ensures that businesses have a clear direction, effective implementation, stakeholder engagement, and proactive risk mitigation. These factors significantly contribute to achieving business success in terms of meeting objectives, delivering value, and maintaining a competitive advantage. The results show that shows that Business success present a positive correlation with project Planning (0. 538). This result suggested that there must be extensive research for Project planning practices and its contribution to business success.

I. INTRODUCTION

Kerzner (2018) defined project management as the application of processes, knowledge, methodology and techniques to achieve a desired outcome. Project management is a crucial discipline that ensures the successful completion of complex tasks and goals within specific timeframes and budgets (Johnson et Al., 2020). It involves the application of knowledge, skills, tools, and techniques to effectively plan, execute, monitor, and control projects. With the increasing complexity and global nature of projects, project management

has become an essential skill for individuals and organizations across various industries.

In order to succeed, the application of project management principles and methodologies is continuously becoming a vital necessity, to guide project managers throughout the project lifespan from Project Initiation to its closure and hence effective project management is crucial for achieving business success as it contributes to effectively align business goals, resource optimization and risk mitigation (Kerzner, 2019). Project management involves effective communication and collaboration with stakeholders, including clients, team members, and other relevant parties, it also includes quality control processes to ensure that deliverables meet the required standards and expectations. It involves monitoring and evaluating project progress, identifying any deviations, and taking corrective actions to maintain quality.

Effective project management allows for adaptability and flexibility in response to changing circumstances or unforeseen challenges (Nachbagauer et Al., 2019). It enables project managers to adjust plans, resources, and strategies to ensure project success despite unexpected obstacles. Project management also promotes a culture of continuous improvement by encouraging lessons learned and best practices. By analyzing project outcomes and feedback, organizations can refine their project management processes and enhance future project success.

Business refers to an ongoing entity or organization that is involved in the production, sale, or provision of goods or services to customers in order to generate profit. It involves various activities such as marketing, operations, finance, and human resources, and is typically focused on long-term sustainability and growth (Daniel C., 2018).

According to Fossen (2021), policymakers consider that businesses, enterprise and small firms, will drive the economic recovery following the 2008 financial crisis which hindered, the economic recovery of many countries for the next five years, as the business sector struggled to gain momentum. Researchers like Meyer and Prashantham (2021) argued that Innovative small businesses that introduce new products,

processes, or business models are more prone to creating fresh markets, experiencing swift growth, and contributing to economic recovery. they may heavily rely on external finance, as they may not have sufficient internal resources to effectively bring their innovations to the market (Xiang et Al., 2018).

➤ *Objectives of the study and research questions*

The general objective of this study is to investigate whether project **planning** practices are effectively applied in community benefits organization and specifically, how it influences business success. In order to attain desired output of this study, the researcher looked out for the answers to the following questions How does project **planning** influence business success? Hypothesis is Project planning does not influence business success.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Contingency Theory

The contingency management theory is a major theoretical lens used to view organizations. It yields many insights and has substantial empirical support since its emergence in the 1970s through Fred Fiedler (Singh 2020).

According to Kerzner (2022), this theory, Project management does not have a universal solution that works for every situation. Instead, the key to success lies in adjusting the management style and techniques to suit the unique circumstances and requirements of each project. Project management helps in identifying and addressing potential risks and challenges, ensuring that the project is managed effectively in different situations

The Contingency Theory suggests that the role of project management in business success is dependent on various factors and circumstances. It recognizes that there is no one-size-fits-all approach to project management and that the effectiveness of project management practices can vary based on the specific context of the organization and the project at hand (Ahmed, 2020).

According to the Contingency Theory, the success of project management in achieving business goals is contingent upon the alignment between the project management approach and the unique characteristics of the project and the organization. This theory emphasizes the need for project managers to adapt their management style, methodologies, and techniques based on the specific requirements and constraints of each project (El Khatib, 2020)

Key factors that influence the effectiveness of project management in business success, according to the Contingency Theory, include:

➤ *Project Complexity*

The level of complexity and uncertainty associated with a project can impact the choice of project management methodologies and the need for more flexible or adaptive approaches (San_Cristóbal, 2018).

Organizational Culture: The culture and values of the organization can influence the project management approach (Kerzner 2018). For example, in a highly hierarchical organization, a more traditional and structured project management approach may be preferred, while in a more innovative and flexible organization, an agile or lean project management approach may be more suitable.

➤ *Stakeholder Expectations*

The needs and expectations of project stakeholders, such as clients, customers, and sponsors, can shape the project management approach. Understanding and managing these expectations is crucial for project success (Ogunberu, 2018)

➤ *Resource Availability*

The availability of resources, including budget, personnel, and technology, can impact the project management approach. Project managers need to consider resource constraints and optimize resource allocation to ensure project success.

➤ *External Environment*

The external environment, including market conditions, regulatory requirements, and industry standards, can influence project management practices. Adapting to external factors is essential for project success.

The contingency theory suggests that project management practices should be tailored to fit the specific circumstances and requirements of each project and organization.

B. Empirical review

Findings by various researchers demonstrate that project management is not just a mere administrative function but a critical aspect of achieving business success. Researchers like Ganiyu and Providence (2020) found out that organizations that prioritize and invest in project management methodologies tend to outperform their competitors and have a higher likelihood of achieving their goals related to efficient resource utilization, improved project success rates, enhanced stakeholder satisfaction, strategic alignment, innovation and adaptability, risk management and gaining competitive advantage. For example, countries like China and Singapore. According to Chen, Fu, Liu, Xu, Zhou and Liu (2019), Project management plays a crucial role in efficiently allocating resources in Chinese businesses. With proper planning and execution, project managers ensure that resources such as time, money, and manpower are utilized effectively, leading to improved productivity and cost savings, hence; the demand for project managers has increased due to the business success

they bring. Kerzner (2018) pointed out that organizations that implement project management have realized the importance of individuals learning an effective methodology to collaborate and achieve success. Project management played the pivotal role in driving the business success in fast paced growing economies like China and Singapore which are booming financial hub on the global level (El Khatib, 2020).

Researchers like Zhao, Hwang, and Lim (2020) argued that Singapore offers scope for project managers from around the world with a promising strategy towards digitalization and sustainability. Based on the recent trends in project managers demand and job offers published on online recruitment platforms, countries like China, India, U.S., Japan, Germany, Australia, UAE and Brazil top the global demand for Project Managers, the PMI points out that organizations worldwide will need 87.7 million people in project management-focused roles by 2027

The research by PMI (2020) revealed that demand for project management-oriented employment (PMOE) in the Sub-Saharan Africa region is predicted to grow by 40% from 2019 to 2030 in order to enhance business success. In sub-Saharan Africa, mainly in Nigeria, South Africa, Kenya and Ghana, this research has identified a cohort of 21 organizations with advanced and high-performing project management offices (PMOs) and which have performed much better compared to the previous year in common indicators of business performance such as revenue, customer loyalty and acquisition, and environment, social, and governance (ESG). It concluded that Africa's economic growth is being hindered primarily by the shortage of skilled project managers.

Nkwabi and Mboya (2019) studied the most significant variables affecting SME growth in Tanzania and found that financial constraints, capital limitations, inadequate technology, and stringent regulations are the primary factors that significantly affect the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Tanzania. According to Project Management Practitioner (PMP), Mugisha (2023) though, there are few institutions offering training in project

management, the demand of PMPs is growing as more organizations in Tanzania are increasingly aware of the project management discipline and its value. Talented project practitioners are needed to face the lack of PM expertise in Tanzania, particularly in the energy sector as well as other mining, drilling, transportation and energy transmission initiatives.

In 2010, the Rwandan Ministry of Trade and Industry reported that SMEs accounted for 98% of businesses and were responsible for 41% of all private-sector employment in the country though, access to finance continues to be a significant hurdle for many micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in Rwanda. Rwanda has made significant progress in recent years in terms of economic development and has become one of the fastest-growing economies in Africa. This growth has been driven by a combination of factors, including a stable political environment, favourable policies, and strong institutions. The project management landscape in Rwanda has become an important area of focus for organizations and policymakers alike (Tilt, Qian, Kuruppu and Dissanayake, 2021). Rwanda's economic growth has been significantly driven by its emphasis on project management and the establishment of a strong project management environment. According to the Rwanda Development Board (RDB, 2020), Rwanda has implemented a successful doing business reform agenda in order to create a favourable and competitive business environment. As a result, Rwanda jumped over 100 places in the World Bank Doing Business Index, today ranking 38th globally and 2nd in Africa and hence project management plays a crucial role in driving business success in Rwanda (Thaddee; Prudence and Valens, 2020).

C. Conceptual Framework

Following the previous paragraphs describing the theoretical framework, a conceptual framework was developed whereby project management practices were presumed to be the project management knowledge areas (PMI, 2008) as the independent variables. The independent variable studied herein are the key factors of Project management and how they influence business success as the dependent variable.

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework
Source: Researcher, 2024

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The research design is the conceptual structure within which results is conducted. It constitutes the blueprint for the collection, measurement and analysis of data (Kothari, 2004). It stands for advance planning of the methods to be adopted for collecting the relevant data and techniques to be used in their analysis.

The study applied descriptive, qualitative and quantitative research designs. These are particularly appropriate for this research because it gives an opportunity for the problem statement to be studied in some depth within a limited time scale (Bell 1999).

First, the researcher collected qualitative data on the extent of project management practices carried out within ABAHIZI CBP. Secondly, qualitative data on the practices was organized into categorical statements and assigned numerical values to enable a quantitative measurement of organizational performance. The role of the project management in ABAHIZI CBP business success was determined through quantitative analytical methods such as descriptive and inferential analysis. Data for the measurement of business success was obtained through survey questionnaire.

B. Study Population, Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

ABAHIZI CBP has been in operations for a decade. Its leadership has Managing Director and a Board of Directors. This study adopted a purposive sampling technique to select the respondents, in total ABAHIZI CBP has 199 personnel, all of whom were considered as the study universe and classified in three categories as follows 18 senior managers, 51 middle managers and ordinal employees and 130 casual workers.

C. Data Collection Methods and Instruments

For this work, the main instrument to collect primary data on project management practices and project performance is questionnaires. The questionnaire is the most appropriate tool as it allowed the researcher to collect information from a sample with diverse background; the findings remained confidential, save time. The questionnaire was presented in a paper format and hence not leave opportunity for bias (Kombo and Tromp, 2006). 199 copies of questionnaires were distributed to all individuals considered to participate in the research, only 177 questionnaires were returned.

D. Validity and Reliability of Research Instrument

The researcher consulted experts who include the supervisor to offer suggestions on content. The researcher also involved some of the colleagues in the master class for their comments. Their recommendations will contribute to reviewing and improvement of the final questionnaires. Prior to the main study, a pretest was conducted on a cohort of 17 participants who did not engage in the actual research to

mitigate potential bias associated with prior exposure to the questionnaire. The outcomes of the pilot test revealed a Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.781, indicating the instrument’s reliability.

Table1:Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.781	17

Source: Researcher’s calculation using SPSS (2023)

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

The collected data underwent organization, tabulation, and analysis employing both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics were employed to analyze responses pertaining to each research question. In parallel, inferential statistics, specifically regression analysis, were utilized to establish relationships between variables.

A. The descriptive analysis of the dependent variable

The following table provides further analysis of the factors which compose the dependent variable.

Table 2: descriptive statistics of dependent variable

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness
Business success	1.53	0.5	0.183
Revenue Growth	1.67	0.581	0.183
Profitability	1.5	0.524	0.183
Customer Satisfaction	1.71	0.566	0.183
Market Share	1.49	0.512	0.183
Return on Investment (ROI)	1.53	0.533	0.183
Employee Satisfaction and Retention	1.46	0.522	0.183
Innovation and Adaptability	1.51	0.523	0.183
Cash Flow Management	1.53	0.544	0.183
Brand Reputation Expansion and Growth	1.45	0.553	0.183

Source: Primary data survey 2023

The table 2 shows that the dependent variable (Business success) encompasses different factors as indicated in the table 5. According to Fred (2009), the evaluation of mean is ranked as between one to four. The Business success evaluation of mean and standards deviation indicate a very satisfactory mean (1.80) and and homogenous of variable (Std.D = .489), this factor include sub-factors which present also a very satisfactory mean and homogeneous of variable. Business success 1.53 (Std.D=.500), Revenue Growth 1.67 (Std.D=.581), Profitability 1.50 (Std.D=.524), Customer Satisfaction 1.71 (Std.D=.566), Market Share 1.49 (Std.D=.512), Return on Investment (ROI) 1.53 (Std.D=.533), Employee Satisfaction and Retention 1.46 (Std.D=.522), Innovation and Adaptability 1.51 (Std.D=.523), Cash Flow

Management 1.53 (Std.D=.544), Brand Reputation Expansion and Growth 1.45 (Std.D=.553) which indicate the high level to be explain by the project management though the result indicate that the variables are normally distributed since the skewness analysis is less than one.

B. The Descriptive analysis of the independent variable

The descriptive analysis for project planning which is the independent variable is carried on different factors. The following table provides the details on factors composing each of the independent variable.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics for independent variables

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness
Project planning	1.8	0.404	0.183
Set clear goals	1.59	0.588	0.183
Allocate resources efficiently	1.73	0.569	0.183
Manage time effectively	1.81	0.527	0.183
Mitigate risks	1.83	0.661	0.183
Foster collaboration	1.66	0.699	0.183
Control costs	1.69	0.619	0.183

Source: Primary data survey 2023

The Project planning has five factors understudy, all also has a strong mean, on Set clear goals 1.59 (Std.D=.588), on Allocate resources efficiently 1.73 (Std.D=.569), on Manage time effectively 1.81 (Std.D=.527), on Mitigate risks 1.83 (Std.D=.661), on Foster collaboration 1.66 (Std.D=.699) and on Control costs 1.69 (Std.D=.619).

Generally, skewness is a measure of the asymmetry of the probability distribution of a real valued random variable about its mean. A negative skew indicates that the tail on the left side of the probability density function is longer or fatter than the right side while a positive skew indicates that the tail on the right side is longer or fatter than the left side; a zero value indicates that the tails on both sides of the mean balance out, which is the case for a symmetric distribution and provide the normal distribution of variable (Zhai et Al.,2022)).

The observed condition is 1. The result provided by the table 5, and table 6 show that all independent and dependent variables results are under 1 and skewed thus the research opt to use the two tail. The following provide the analysis on how variable correlate each other.

C. Correlation analysis

The correlation is one of the most common and most useful statistics. Linear correlation coefficient, measures the strength and the direction of a linear relationship between two variables (Schober P. et Al., 2018).

Table 4: Correlation analysis

		Business success	Project planning
Business success	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	177	
Project planning	Pearson Correlation	.538**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	
	N	177	177

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Primary data survey 2023

The Table 4 shows that Business success present a positive correlation with project Planning (0.538) and a slightly weak correlation to project Execution (0.582), a positive correlation with Stakeholder management plan (0.608) and a positive correction with risk management plan (0.582).

The result from the Table 7. shows again that project planning posits a weak positive correction with project execution (0. 310), Stakeholder management plan (0. 148) and Risk management plan (0. 178)

The table 7 shows that Project execution posits a strong positive correlation with Stakeholder management plan (0. 399) and Risk management plan (0. 272), while Stakeholder management plan posits a strong positive correlation with Risk management plan (0.363)

D. Multiple regression analysis

Regression analysis was computed to establish the degree of effect which project planning variable has on each factor of project performance (dependent variable). The discussion of relationship between project management predictors and Business success factors tested by multiple linear regression model are presented below (Nizeyimana A., 2022)

Assume 5% level of significance, and test the following hypothesis: H0: $\beta=0$ (\approx this means that there is no relationship between Project management and Business success) H1: $\beta\neq 0$ (\approx this means that there is a relationship between Project management and Business success). Below you can see two ways of testing the above hypothesis. We must determine whether we can trust the above coefficient values or if the relationships are caused by natural variation.

Approach 1 (Comparing the t-statistic to a t-table or a z-table): Compare the t-test statistic (for the coefficient β) with a critical value from a t-table (or a z-table under some circumstances, the number of degrees of freedom for a t-test is computed as: d.f.= number of observations – 1 constant – number of estimated slope parameters in the regression.

H0 is rejected if the (t-statistic) > (t critical value). => We believe in H1.

H0 cannot be rejected if the (t-statistic) < (t critical value). => We do not believe in H1.

In regression, the decomposition of the total sum of squares (SST) into the “explained” sum of squares (SSR) and the “unexplained” sum of squares (SSE) took place in the Analysis of Variance or ANOVA table. However, ANOVA also refers to a statistical technique used to test for differences between the means for several populations. While the procedure is related to regression, in ANOVA the independent variable(s) are qualitative rather than quantitative. In both regression and ANOVA, the dependent variable is quantitative (Nizeyimana A., 2022).

As usual, we rely on a hypothesis test to determine if the sample means for the k samples drawn (one from each population) differ enough for the difference to be statistically significant (more than would likely occur due to random chance alone).

Hypotheses

$$\text{Test Statistic: } F = \frac{MSR}{MSE},$$

where MSR = the Mean Square for Treatments, and MSE = the Mean Square for Error

Note: MSR is often called MST in the literature and MSR is used to highlight the similarity between regression and analysis of variance. MSE remains the same for both regression and analysis of variance

E. Analysis of the Business Success and project management

The Combined model analysis is composed with Business success as dependent variable with Risk management plan, Project planning, Project execution, Stakeholder management plan. The following tables provide the analysis of the regression model.

Table 5: Combined model review

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.803 ^a	0.645	0.636	0.302

The table 5 show that the R square is 0.645 such as 64.5 percent which is acceptable when considering project scope, budget planning, communication plan and risk management planning as independent variables factors and project result as dependent variable. The following table provides the analysis of variance.

Table 6: Analysis of variance for the combined model review

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	28.416	4	7.104	78.008	.000 ^b
	Residual	15.663	172	0.091		
	Total	44.079	176			

a. Dependent Variable: Business success

b. Predictors: (Constant), Risk management plan, Project planning, Project execution, Stakeholder management plan

The result from the table 6 indicates that the sum of squares for the regression model is 28.416 while mean of square in regression model is 7.104 which is fairly significant toward the relationship of independent and dependent variable. Thus, the analysis involves comparing the probability condition where the expected value for the predicted variables is less than 0.05, The outcome indicates that the variance and sum of squares meet the criteria and are satisfactory. As a result, the full model also yields a significant value of 0.000. The table below presents a detailed analysis of the significance level of each independent variable in order to determine if there is a significant factor in project management.

Table 7: detailed analysis of the significance level

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-0.573	0.125		-4.575	0.000
	Project planning	0.344	0.062	0.277	5.575	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Business success

The table 7 shows that all of independent variables have positive and significant effect on business Success. Project planning with β=0.277, with β= 0.271, Stakeholder management plan with β= 0.298 and Risk management plan with β=0.269. Thus, a number of variables from independent variables influence the business success at Abahizi CBC.

The study revealed that performing project planning, project execution, stakeholder management plan, and risk management plan ensures that businesses have a clear direction, effective implementation, stakeholder engagement, and proactive risk mitigation. These factors significantly contribute to achieving business success in terms of meeting objectives, delivering value, and maintaining a competitive advantage

F. Hypothesis testing

➤ Model 1: Testing Ho1 (Project planning and Business success)

$$f = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PPI_1 + \beta_2 PPI_2 + \beta_3 PPI_3 + \beta_4 PPI_4 + \beta_5 PPI_5 + \beta_6 PPI_6 + \epsilon_0$$

➤ Hypothesis 1:

H0(1): There exist no significant relationship between project planning and projects Business success Abahizi CBC.

Table 8 : Project planning and Business success

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	-0.09	0.203		-0.43	0.67	-0.487	0.315
Set clear goals	0.14	0.056	0.164	2.518	0.01	0.03	0.249
Allocate resources efficiently	0.271	0.059	0.308	4.588	0	0.154	0.387
Manage time effectively	0.197	0.063	0.208	3.138	0	0.073	0.321
Mitigate risks	0.149	0.05	0.197	2.963	0	0.05	0.248
Foster collaboration	0.096	0.047	0.134	2.02	0.05	0.002	0.19
Control costs	0.082	0.053	0.101	1.549	0.12	-0.022	0.186

Source: Researcher’s calculation using SPSS (2023)

Therefore, in this case, we have 6 degrees of freedom. The critical value for the t-test is 1.440 for 90%, 1.943 for 95%, and 3.143 for 99%.

➤ T-Test and β coefficient (estimate)

Based on table 11, the equation for the regression line is:

$$f = -0.09 + 0.14 X_1 + 0.271 X_2 + 0.197 X_3 + 0.149 X_4 + 0.096 X_5 + 0.082 X_6 + \epsilon$$

According to the intercept (β0), when the six project planning variables are hold constant, the value of business success at ABAHIZI was -0.009. Planning resources are well defined (estimate of 0.196, t statistic of 7.921)

The results from table 8 shows that project planning variables: Set clear goals (estimate of 0.14, t statistic of 2.518), Allocate resources efficiently (estimate of 0.271, t statistic of 4.588), Manage time effectively (estimate of 0.197, t statistic of 3.138), Mitigate risks (estimate of 0.149, t statistic of 2.963), Foster collaboration (estimate of 0.096, t statistic of 2.02) are significant at 95% of confidence level and only Control costs (estimate of 0.082, t statistic of 1.549) not significant by comparing its t-calculated and t-value (t statistic < 1.943). The results showed that all predictors had a positive effect.

➤ Adjusted R2 and Coefficient of determination (R2)

The table 9 below shows the model summary of the effect of the project planning variable on the business success at Abahizi CBC.

Table 9 : Model summary. Project planning and business success

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.560 ^a	0.313	0.289	0.422

Source: Researcher’s calculation using SPSS (2023)

By normalizing the model, the percentage of variation was shifted from 31.3% (R²=R square) to 28.9% (adjusted R square). The project planning variables studied affect at 28.9% on the business success at Abahizi CBC as represented by the R². It means that 28.9% of variation in business success were explained by the variation in project planning variables. While the remaining of 71.1% can be attributed to other variables not considered by this study model

Table 10.: ANOVA results of effect of project planning on the Business success

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.816	6	2.303	12.935	.000 ^b
	Residual	30.263	170	0.178		
	Total	44.079	176			

Source: Researcher’s calculation using SPSS (2023)

The results from table 10 The analysis of variance was used to determine whether the model is a good fit for the data. The Results indicated that the overall model was statistically significant. The project planning variables are the good predictors of Business success. The P-value or significance value is .000 and F calculated value is 12.935. As the F

calculated $=12.935 > F_{\text{Critical}} = 2.164$ at $\alpha = 0.05$, this means that the model is statistically significant. $H_0(1)$ is rejected and accept H_1 , and conclude that there exists a positive significant relationship between project planning and Business success at Abahizi CBC

G. Impact of project planning on business success

The study findings indicated that Project planning contribute to Business success at ABAHIZI CBP with a mean score of 1.80. According to the results, the study established that project planning has an effect on the business success of ABAHIZI CBP. Planning resources are defined by Setting clear goals, allocating resources efficiently and Controlling costs, managing time effectively but also fostering collaboration to mitigate risks. The study concludes that project planning has an impact on business success. By Model 1 concluded that there exists a positive significant relationship between project planning and Business success at ABAHIZI CBP.

V. DISCUSSIONS

The data was obtained through administration of questionnaires to 177 respondents. The targeted population of this study was 199 respondents, but the researcher found only 177 respondents to participate to the study. This gave a response rate of 88.9%. According to Nizeyimana A. (2022), a response rate of 50% is adequate for a study, 60% is good and 70% and above is excellent. Thus, a response rate of 88.9 % of our study was fit and reliable for the study. The findings of the study indicated that the project planning predictors studied has an effect to business success at ABAHIZI CBP.

The study concurs with the study of Kerzner (2018) who asserted that Project management is essential in the business sector as it enables organizations to effectively plan, execute and control. The results indicated that project planning variable has influence on Business success. The findings agreed with (Pirozzi M.,2018) who showed that the achievement of the project goal may be limited by various factors such as scope, quality, schedule, budget, resources, risks, customer satisfaction, and stakeholder involvement.

The findings of the study confirm the ones from Mishra, A. K. (2019). In his work of Assessment of project performance in terms of time cost and quality show that planning in terms of schedule management and human resource management inhibit cost performance.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The general objective of this study is to investigate whether project planning practices are effectively applied in community benefits organization and specifically to analyze how it influences business success The general objective for this research is to analyze the impact of effective project management practices on overall business success while the

specifics objectives were to investigate the impact of project planning on business success, to determine the influence of project execution on business success, to determine the effect of risk management on business success and to determine the influence of stakeholder management on and business outcomes. The data were collected at ABAHIZI CBP.

The researcher concludes that the study was successfully conducted, results achieved, research questions answered, and the research objectives have been attained. The strengths found in this research was the positive relationship between the project management factors which allows the business success. The results indicated that the project management predictors under study had effect on business success and that variation in business success were explained by the variation in project management predictors under the study all of which posited a positive relationship with business success but on small percentages and this constitutes the weaknesses found in this research study.

From the analysis and discussion of the result, it is undoubted that research question and objective of this research were clearly addressed. The results show that shows that Business success present a positive correlation with project Planning (0.538) Hence, in order to achieve business success, project manager must strongly focus on planning of all projects to be carried out under the organization and well execute the plans to attain the intended goals and objectives.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Ahmed, W., Najmi, A., & Ikram, M. (2020). Steering firm performance through innovative capabilities: A contingency approach to innovation management. *Technology in Society*, 63, 101385.
- [2]. Chen, T., Fu, M., Liu, R., Xu, X., Zhou, S., & Liu, B. (2019). How do project management competencies change within the project management career model in large Chinese construction companies?. *International Journal of project management*, 37(3), 485-500.
- [3]. Cszaszar, F. A., & Ostler, J. (2020). A contingency theory of representational complexity in organizations. *Organization Science*, 31(5), 1198-1219.
- [4]. Daniel, C. O. (2018). Effects of marketing strategies on organizational performance. *International journal of business marketing and management*, 3(9), 1-9.
- [5]. El Khatib, M., Alabdooli, K., AlKaabi, A., & Al Harmoodi, S. (2020). Sustainable Project Management: Trends and Alignment. *Theoretical Economics Letters*, 10(06), 1276.
- [6]. Elia, G., Margherita, A., & Secundo, G. (2021). Project management canvas: a systems thinking framework to address project complexity. *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*, 14(4), 809-835.
- [7]. Fossen, F. M. (2021). Self-employment over the business cycle in the USA: a decomposition. *Small Business Economics*, 57(4), 1837-1855.

- [8]. Ganiyu, S. A., Yu, D., Xu, C., & Providence, A. M. (2020). The impact of supply chain risks and supply chain risk management strategies on enterprise performance in Ghana. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 8(4), 1491-1507.
- [9]. Jawahar, I. M., & McLaughlin, G. L. (2018). Toward a descriptive stakeholder theory: An organizational life cycle approach. In *Business Ethics and Strategy*, Volumes I and II (pp. 381-398). Routledge.
- [10]. Johnson, M. R., Bolte, J., Veldman, T., & Sutton, L. (2020). Establishing a Project Management Community of Practice in a Large Academic Health System. *Journal of Research Administration*, 51(2), 102-113.
- [11]. Kerzner, (2019). Using the project management maturity model: strategic planning for project management. John Wiley & Sons.
- [12]. Kerzner, H. (2018). *Project management best practices: Achieving global excellence*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [13]. Kerzner, H. (2022). *Project management metrics, KPIs, and dashboards: a guide to measuring and monitoring project performance*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [14]. Meyer, K. E., Prashantham, S., & Xu, S. (2021). Entrepreneurship and the post-COVID-19 recovery in emerging economies. *Management and Organization Review*, 17(5), 1101-1118.
- [15]. Nachbagauer, A. G., & Schirl-Boeck, I. (2019). Managing the unexpected in megaprojects: riding the waves of resilience. *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*, 12(3), 694-715.
- [16]. Nizeyimana Aimé Adrien. (2022). Project planning practices and the cost performance of local government projects in Rwanda. *Global scientific journal*, 10, 2320-9186.
<http://coi.citefactor.org/10.11216/gsj.2022.11.89472>
- [17]. Nkwabi, J., & Mboya, L. (2019). A review of factors affecting the growth of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Tanzania. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 11(33), 1-8.
- [18]. Ogunberu, A. O., Akintelu, S. O., & Olaposi, T. O. (2018). Application of project scope management practices on project success among telecommunication organizations in Nigeria. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 7(2), 518-532.
- [19]. othari, C. R. (2004). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Age International.
- [20]. Pirozzi, M. (2018). The stakeholder management perspective to increase the success rate of complex projects. *PM World Journal*, 7(1), 1-12.
- [21]. Project Management Institute (PMI). (2020). *PMI 2020 Signposts Report: 6 Global Business Trends Driving The Project Economy and What They Mean for Project Leaders*. PMI Thought Leadership.
- [22]. Reed, J. E., Howe, C., Doyle, C., & Bell, D. (2018). Simple rules for evidence translation in complex systems: a qualitative study. *BMC medicine*, 16, 1-20.
- [23]. San Cristóbal, J. R., Carral, L., Diaz, E., Fraguera, J. A., & Iglesias, G. (2018). Complexity and project management: A general overview. *Complexity*, 2018.
- [24]. Schober, P., Boer, C., & Schwarte, L. A. (2018). Correlation coefficients: appropriate use and interpretation. *Anesthesia & analgesia*, 126(5), 1763-1768.
- [25]. Singh, R., Ramdeo, S., Singh, R., & Ramdeo, S. (2020). Organizational-Level Theories. *Leading Organizational Development and Change: Principles and Contextual Perspectives*, 247-260.
- [26]. Thaddee, B., Prudence, N., & Valens, S. (2020). Influence of project management practices on project success in Rwanda-the case of Girinka project in Runda sector, Kamonyi district, Rwanda. *European Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, 5(3).
- [27]. Tilt, C. A., Qian, W., Kuruppu, S., & Dissanayake, D. (2021). The state of business sustainability reporting in sub-Saharan Africa: an agenda for policy and practice. *Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal*, 12(2), 267-296.
- [28]. Xiang, D., Zhang, Y., & Worthington, A. C. (2018, March). Determinants of the use of fintech finance among Chinese small and medium-sized enterprises. In *2018 IEEE international symposium on innovation and entrepreneurship (TEMS-ISIE)* (pp. 1-10). IEEE.
- [29]. Zhai, J., Bai, M., & Hao, J. (2022). Uncertain random mean-variance-skewness models for the portfolio optimization problem. *Optimization*, 71(13), 3941-3964.